

The effect of laughter yoga on premenstrual syndrome symptoms and quality of life in young women: A randomised controlled trial protocol

Genç kadınlara uygulanan kahkaha yogasının premenstrual sendrom semptomlarına ve yaşam kalitesine etkisi: Randomize kontrollü çalışma protokolü

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ABSTRACT

Aim: This protocol aims to present the design of a study seeking to determine the effect of laughter yoga applied to young women on premenstrual syndrome symptoms and quality of life.

Material and Methods: This study was designed as a parallel-group randomized controlled trial with pre-test, mid-test, and post-test assessments. The sample consisted of 72 women aged 18–25 years (36 intervention, 36 control) randomly assigned to groups via power analysis. The intervention group participated in laughter yoga sessions twice weekly for four weeks, followed by four more weeks of daily self-laughter practice. The control group received no intervention during the study period but received one session after the study was completed. Measurements to assess the effectiveness and sustainability of the intervention were taken at baseline, week 4, and week 8.

Results: The findings of this study are expected to demonstrate that laughter yoga, a drug-free, low-cost, risk-free method that is easily learned and applied by individuals, is an effective complementary and sustainable approach in reducing the severity of premenstrual syndrome symptoms and improving the quality of life of individuals.

Conclusion: The reduction in symptoms may contribute to a decrease in healthcare utilization and workload, and a reduction in direct and indirect healthcare costs. Furthermore, the findings are expected to provide an evidence-based foundation for holistic nursing care practices and encourage the more widespread use of complementary and supportive methods in the management of premenstrual syndrome in both clinical and academic settings.

ÖZ

Amaç: Bu protokol, genç kadınlara uygulanan kahkaha yogasının adet öncesi sendromu semptomları ve yaşam kalitesi üzerindeki etkisini belirlemeyi amaçlayan bir çalışmanın tasarımını sunmayı hedeflemektedir.

Materyaller ve yöntemler: Bu çalışma, ön test, ara test ve son test içeren paralel gruplu randomize kontrollü bir çalışma olarak tasarlanmıştır. Örneklem, 18-25 yaş arası 72 kadından (36 müdahale, 36 kontrol) oluşmuştur. Örneklem büyüklüğü güç analizi ile belirlenmiş; uygun katılımcılar rastgele atanmıştır. Müdahale grubu, dört hafta boyunca haftada iki kez (her biri 30-40 dakika) kahkaha yogası seanslarına katılmıştır. Müdahale döneminden sonra bir ara test değerlendirmesi yapılmıştır. Daha sonra katılımcılardan dört hafta boyunca günlük olarak kahkaha egzersizleri yapmaları istenmiştir. Müdahalenin sürdürülebilirliğini ve etkinliğini değerlendirmek için 8. haftada son ölçümler alınmıştır. Kontrol grubu, çalışma süresi boyunca herhangi bir müdahale almamıştır; ancak etik ilkelere uygun olarak, çalışmanın tamamlanmasının ardından bir kahkaha yogası seansı sağlanmıştır. Ölçümler başlangıçta, 4. haftada ve 8. haftada yapılmıştır.

Bulgular: Bu çalışmanın bulgularının, kahkaha yogasının; ilaçsız, düşük maliyetli, risksiz ve bireyler tarafından kolayca öğrenilip uygulanabilen bir yöntem olarak, premenstrüel sendrom belirtilerinin şiddetini azaltmada ve bireylerin yaşam kalitesini artırmada etkili, tamamlayıcı ve sürdürülebilir bir yaklaşım olduğunu göstermesi beklenmektedir.

Sonuç: Semptomlardaki azalma, sağlık hizmeti kullanımında ve iş yükünde azalmaya ve doğrudan ve dolaylı sağlık hizmeti maliyetlerinde azalmaya katkıda bulunabilir. Ayrıca, bulguların bütüncül hemşirelik bakım uygulamaları için kanıta dayalı bir temel sağlaması ve hem klinik hem de akademik ortamlarda adet öncesi sendromun yönetiminde tamamlayıcı ve destekleyici yöntemlerin daha yaygın kullanımını teşvik etmesi beklenmektedir.

ARTICLE INFO/MAKALE BİLGİSİ

Keywords; Premenstrual syndrome, laughter yoga, quality of life

Anahtar kelimeler; Premenstrual sendrom, kahkaha yogası, yaşam kalitesi

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INTRODUCTION

The menstrual cycle is defined as the periodic preparatory process that occurs regularly in the female reproductive system, beginning in puberty, and necessary for ovulation and pregnancy. Amenorrhoea, dysmenorrhoea, abnormal uterine bleeding, and Premenstrual Syndrome (PMS) are the most common problems encountered in the reproductive cycle (1). PMS is a condition characterised by physical, behavioural, and psychological symptoms that emerge during the luteal phase of the menstrual cycle and diminish or disappear with the onset of menstruation. It is not associated with any underlying psychiatric disorder and negatively impacts an individual's quality of life (2-4). Although the factors causing PMS are not fully understood, genetic factors, ovarian activity, oestradiol and progesterone levels, neurotransmitters such as serotonin and gamma-aminobutyric acid, renin-angiotensin imbalance, and low endogenous endorphins are thought to contribute to PMS (5).

The prevalence of premenstrual syndrome varies across different populations. Studies conducted in Turkey have determined that the prevalence of PMS among young women ranges from 50.3% to 58.1%, reaching up to 59% among high school students (6,7). A meta-analysis conducted in Africa showed that the prevalence of PMS among women of reproductive age ranged from 43.8% to 57.32%. Among young women, it was found to range between 38.6% and 66.04% (8). In a large-scale study conducted in India, the overall prevalence of PMS was 43%, while among young people, this rate was found to be 49.6% (9). According to studies conducted in different ethnic groups and countries in the literature, it has been reported that 90% of women of reproductive age experience at least one or two mild PMS symptoms, while 20-40% experience these symptoms

severely enough to affect their social life. Furthermore, it has been found that 2-8% of women develop Premenstrual Dysphoric Disorder (PMDD), defined as the most severe form of PMS (2, 10, 11). A systematic review by Gao and colleagues indicated that premenstrual symptoms affect 90% of women of reproductive age (11).

The symptoms and severity of PMS vary between individuals and encompass a wide range of psychological, physical, and behavioural symptoms. Psychological symptoms include depression, irritability, outbursts of anger, crying spells, anxiety, restlessness, confusion, social withdrawal, difficulty concentrating, forgetfulness, feelings of guilt, paranoia, hypersensitivity to sound and light, depressive mood, and feelings of loss of control (12). Physical symptoms include breast tenderness/fullness, bloating, weight changes, headaches, oedema, muscle and joint pain, hot flushes, skin problems, and gastrointestinal discomfort (2). Behavioural symptoms include changes in sexual desire, insomnia, disruption of work habits, avoidance of human relationships, tendency to fight, apathy, and social withdrawal, among more than 200 different psychological, physical, and behavioural symptoms (1-3, 12). These symptoms affect women's daily lives in multiple ways and reduce their quality of life. PMS symptoms negatively affect not only physical but also cognitive and emotional functioning (12).

Quality of life is a comprehensive and dynamic concept that is shaped by the interaction of an individual's physical and psychological health with social and environmental factors and is assessed based on the complex relationships between an individual's health status, psychosocial well-being, and environmental conditions (13). Research has shown that women experiencing PMS have negatively affected interpersonal relationships, reduced

participation in the workforce, and increased absenteeism. Furthermore, PMS has been shown to cause a decrease in productivity and efficiency, to be associated with a lack of self-confidence, and to negatively affect quality of life (13-16).

Both pharmacological and non-pharmacological methods are used in the management of premenstrual symptoms. Pharmacological treatments include progesterone, oral contraceptives, antidepressants such as SSRIs and SNRIs, diuretics, vitamin and mineral supplements, analgesics, and anxiolytics (4). Non-pharmacological methods include reflexology (12), cognitive behavioural therapy, exercise, massage (4), yoga (17), aromatherapy (12), phytotherapy, and acupuncture (3). As pharmacological treatments can cause certain side effects (fatigue, headaches, mood swings, gastrointestinal bleeding, etc.), women are increasingly turning to non-pharmacological methods due to their accessibility, fewer side effects, and economic advantages (3, 4, 12). Laughter yoga is one such method. Laughter yoga can reduce stress by releasing endorphins and alleviate these symptoms by improving mood. Laughing can reduce muscle pain and tension by increasing the production of neurotransmitters such as dopamine and serotonin (18). In their study, Karali & Gürkan (2024) stated that laughter yoga reduces stress levels, increases happiness hormones, and strengthens the immune system (19). It has been found that laughter yoga contributes to alleviating symptoms arising during PMS, pregnancy, childbirth, and cancer treatments and improves quality of life (18, 19). This method stands out as a potential intervention in reducing the effects of PMS and can improve the quality of life for young women.

Laughter yoga is a holistic practice that combines breathing exercises, physical relaxation, and laughter practices to provide both physical and mental relaxation. With these characteristics, it is a combination of methods previously used in PMS management. In this study, participants are encouraged to continue regular laughter practice after the interim measurement during the intervention process, with the aim of ensuring individual sustainability. Thus, not only short-term effects but also the effects of the intervention that are spread over time and become established in the individual can be evaluated. Furthermore, the fact that the initiative is individually applicable and cost-free offers a significant advantage in terms of sustainability. In this respect, laughter yoga aims to contribute to the midwifery literature an evidence-based, innovative, and feasible intervention approach for managing PMS symptoms.

Study Aim

This study aims to determine the effects of laughter yoga on young women's premenstrual syndrome symptom management and quality of life using a holistic approach. In this regard, the hypotheses of the study are as follows:

H0₁: There is no significant difference in premenstrual syndrome symptoms between young individuals with premenstrual syndrome who practise laughter yoga and young individuals with premenstrual syndrome who do not practise laughter yoga.

H0₂: There is no significant difference in quality of life between young individuals with premenstrual syndrome who practise laughter yoga and young individuals with premenstrual syndrome who do not practise laughter yoga.

H0: There is no significant difference in PMSÖ total scores and subscale scores between young individuals with premenstrual syndrome who practised laughter yoga and young individuals with premenstrual syndrome who did not practise laughter yoga.

H0: There is no significant difference in terms of total quality of life scale scores and subscale scores between young individuals with premenstrual syndrome who practised laughter yoga and young individuals with premenstrual syndrome who did not practise laughter yoga.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study design

The study was designed as a randomised controlled trial. The study protocol was registered in ClinicalTrials under number NCT07139223.

Setting

The study is planned to be conducted at the Bilecik Şeyh Edebali University Vocational School of Health Services during the autumn semester of the 2025-2026 academic year. The application is expected to take place in a playroom located in the vocational school building, which has an approximate area of 75 m² and is equipped with mats and cushions.

Participants

The population of the study will consist of female students enrolled at the Bilecik Şeyh Edebali University Vocational School of Health Services. A power analysis was conducted to determine the number of participants to be included in the study. The power of the test was calculated using the G*Power 3.1 programme. In a similar study in the relevant literature conducted by Kucukkelepce and colleagues (2020), the effect size related to the change in quality of life was calculated

as 0.589. In order for the power of the study to exceed 95%, it is necessary to reach 66 participants, with 33 participants in each group, at a 5% significance level and an effect size of 0.589 (df=32; t=1.694). Given the high power of the test and in line with the general literature, the study aimed to recruit 72 participants in total, with 36 participants in each group, accounting for a 10% loss.

Inclusion criteria:

- Experiencing premenstrual symptoms (PMS score of 110 points or higher),
- Aged 18–25 (20,21),
- Having regular menstruation,
- Able to read and understand Turkish,

Exclusion criteria:

- Incomplete completion of pre-test data collection forms,
- Students with chronic illness requiring continuous medication,
- Students using hormonal contraceptive methods,
- Students with any health issues that may create communication barriers,
- Students receiving treatment for insomnia (e.g., SSRIs and SNRIs),
- Receiving treatment for PMS,
- Having been pregnant or lactating in the last 12 months,
- Regularly exercising (affecting homogeneity between groups, intervention effectiveness, etc.),
- Having a diagnosed psychiatric illness (depression, panic attacks, schizophrenia, etc.),

- Those with a condition preventing them from participating in laughter yoga (having undergone abdominal surgery in the past three months, uncontrolled hypertension, glaucoma, hernia, epilepsy)
- Failure to attend any of the laughter yoga sessions,
- Occurrence of any exclusion criteria during the study (e.g., diagnosis of a psychiatric disorder, initiation of medication, pregnancy),
- Students who do not participate in the final test will be excluded from the study.

Variables and Outcomes

This study will apply laughter yoga intervention to young women aged 18–25 with PMS in order to reduce PMS symptoms and improve quality of life. The program is planned to last 8 weeks.

The Participant Information Form is a form that contains participants’ demographic information and information about their menstrual cycles. The participant information form has been specially prepared by the researchers.

The Premenstrual Syndrome Scale (PMSÖ) is a five-point Likert-type scale consisting of 44 questions designed to measure the severity of premenstrual symptoms, based on DSM-III and DSM-IV-R, developed by Gençdoğan (2006) (22). In scoring the scale, the ‘Never’ option is scored as 1 point, the ‘Very rarely’ option as 2 points, the ‘Sometimes’ option as 3 points, the ‘Often’ option as 4 points, and the ‘Always’ option as 5 points. The scale consists of nine subscales: depressive mood, anxiety, fatigue, irritability, depressive thoughts, pain, appetite changes, sleep changes, and bloating. The scale can yield a minimum score of 44 and a maximum score of 220.

Table 1. Research Outcome Variables

Result Type	Variables
Primary Outcomes	PMS Symptom Severity Quality of Life Level
Secondary Outcomes	PMSS ve DSÖYK-KF Score

Data Collection Tools:

The research data will be collected using the Participant Inclusion/Exclusion Control Form, Personal Information Form, Premenstrual Syndrome Scale, World Health Organisation Quality of Life Scale - Short Form (WHOQOL-SF) and Laughter Practices Daily Tracking Form.

The Participant Inclusion/Exclusion Control Form is a form that determines whether an individual meets the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the study before starting the study.

An increase in the scale score indicates an increase in the intensity of PMS symptoms. If the total scale score exceeds 50% (110) of the total scale score (220) on the PMS scale, PMS is considered to be ‘present’. The total Cronbach’s alpha reliability coefficient of the scale is 0.75, and the Cronbach’s alpha coefficients of the sub-dimensions range from 0.75 to 0.91.

The World Health Organisation Quality of Life Scale - Short Form (WHOQOL-SF) was developed in 1980 to define quality of life by the World Health Organisation (WHO) and

15 centres from various countries, enabling cross-cultural comparisons (23). It was adapted into Turkish by Eser and colleagues (1999) in our country (24). The scale consists of 27 questions covering four domains: physical health, psychological health, social relationships, and environment. Questions are answered based on the last 15 days. Each question is scored from 1 to 5, with scores ranging from 0 to 100. When calculating the DSÖYKÖ-KF score, items 1 and 2 are evaluated independently, while the responses obtained from questions 3, 4, 26, and 27 are reversed because they indicate negativity. Since the scale does not have a total score, four subscale scores are evaluated: physical health, social relationships, psychological health, and environmental domain. Higher scores on the scale indicate a higher quality of life. The DSÖYKÖ-KF Cronbach's Alpha values for the subscales are 0.83 for physical, 0.66 for psychological, 0.53 for social, and 0.73 for environmental.

• Laughter Practice Daily Tracking Form

This form was developed by the researchers to monitor the laughter practice applications given to participants as daily homework after the interim test measurements were taken in the study.

Data Collection

Randomisation

In the study, participants will be assigned to the intervention and control groups using a random assignment method. Through random assignment, each participant will be distributed equally and impartially among the groups, thereby reducing the risk of selection bias and minimising the probability of Type I error (25).

To ensure there is no bias in the individuals included in the study, random assignment

will be performed. The random assignment table was created using the website '<https://www.calculatorsoup.com>'. Participants will be randomly assigned to groups using the random assignment table. In addition, the random assignment process of the study will be presented in accordance with the CONSORT 2025 statement (26).

Blinding

Due to the nature of the intervention, blinding of participants and researchers was not feasible in this study. However, to minimise potential bias, blinding was implemented at the data analysis stage. The collected data were coded as "Group 1" and "Group 2" representing the intervention and control groups, and statistical analyses were performed by an independent statistician who was blinded to group allocation. Thus, the study was conducted with single-blind (statistician-blinded) design.

Formation of Intervention and Control Groups

Preparation Process: The researcher has received Laughter Yoga Leader training.

The formation of the intervention and control groups in the study is planned to be carried out as described below.

Information and Consent Process: A randomised controlled experimental design will be used in the study. Female students studying at the Vocational School of Health Services will be informed about the planned research. Participants who volunteer to participate in the research will be evaluated in terms of inclusion criteria. The PMSÖ will be administered to participants who meet the inclusion criteria according to the Inclusion Criteria Form. Verbal and written consent and contact information will be obtained from participants who meet the criteria.

Pre-test Application: A pre-test will be conducted by administering the participant information form and DSÖYKÖ-KF to individuals who score 110 points or above on the PMSÖ.

Group Assignment: 72 participants who score 110 or higher on the PMSÖ scale will be randomly assigned to intervention and control groups using a computer-assisted random number table.

The codes of the 72 participants will be written down and placed in a bag, and participants will be assigned to the intervention or control group according to the randomisation list.

Contact details will be obtained during the first interview with the students. All interviews will be conducted face-to-face at the university. Each participant will have a different code.

A computer-assisted simple randomisation method will be used to ensure that participants are distributed homogeneously across the experimental and control groups. The randomisation process will be created by an impartial researcher not involved in the study. Participants will not be informed about the groups they are in; only the researcher will know which group they are in, ensuring single-blindness (statistician) in the study.

Steps Taken for the Intervention Group

In order to conduct laughter yoga as a nursing intervention, the researcher obtained a 'laughter yoga leadership certificate'. After explaining the purpose of the study to the participants, written informed consent will be obtained from individuals who voluntarily agree to participate in the study. Following completion of the consent process, inclusion and exclusion criteria will be applied for pre-intervention assessment. Subsequently, the Premenstrual Syndrome Scale will be administered to participants. Individuals

scoring 110 points or higher on the scale will undergo randomisation after the DSÖYKÖ-KF is administered. All scales used in the study will be administered to participants face-to-face, and pre-test data will be collected in this manner.

Following the pre-test, the laughter yoga intervention will be conducted for the experimental group over four weeks, consisting of two sessions per week for a total of eight sessions. Following the completion of the intervention process, an interim test will be administered to participants for interim evaluation purposes. After this assessment, participants in the intervention group will be asked to practise laughter regularly every day for four weeks, and these practices will be given as homework.

At the end of the four-week individual practice period, the same scales will be re-administered to assess the sustainability and effectiveness of the intervention, and final test data will be collected in this way.

After the mid-measurement is completed, structured laughter practices, which are expected to be performed individually every day for four weeks, will be applied to the intervention group. These practices consist of techniques developed by Master Laughter Yoga Instructor Şengül Esen Demir, who is competent in the field of laughter yoga, and adapted for individual use. Participants performed laughter practices individually three times a day (morning, noon, and evening).

At the end of the four-week individual application process, the same scales will be reapplied to the intervention and control groups to assess the sustainability and effectiveness level of the intervention, and final test data will be collected in this manner. No intervention was made to the control

group, and this group continued their normal daily routines. After the training is completed and the final tests are conducted, the same training will also be provided to the control group.

Data analysis

The data obtained in the study will be analysed using the SPSS (Statistical Package for Social Sciences) for Windows 22.0 programme. The Kolmogorov Smirnov Test will be used to determine whether the research data is normally distributed. According to the Kolmogorov Smirnov Test, if $p > 0.05$, the distribution is determined to be normal. However, if $p < 0.05$, the distribution is determined to be non-normal, and the Skewness and Kurtosis values of the data are examined. If the Skewness and Kurtosis values are between +2 and -2, the variable is considered to be normally distributed (27). The homogeneity of descriptive characteristics between groups will be tested using chi-square analysis. If the data are normally distributed, the t-test will be used to evaluate the difference between the means of two independent groups; if the data are not normally distributed, the Mann-Whitney U test will be used. Changes in measurements within the group will be analysed using the repeated measures ANOVA test if the data are normally distributed, and the Friedman test if the data are not normally distributed.

The primary outcomes of the study will be the changes in premenstrual syndrome symptom severity and quality of life over time. The main analysis will focus on group-by-time interaction effects for both outcomes.

In cases of missing data, appropriate statistical methods will be applied to handle missing values to minimize bias. Furthermore, all analyses will be conducted according to the intention-to-treat (ITT) principle, in which

all participants will be analysed in the groups to which they were originally assigned.

Ethics

Prior to the research, ethical approval was obtained from the Scientific Research Ethics Committee of Lokman Hekim University (Date: 27.06.2025, Code No: 2025174, Decision No: 2025/178); additionally, institutional permission was obtained from Bilecik Şeyh Edebali University. Participants who agree to participate in the research will be informed verbally and in writing about the purpose of the study, that their personal information will be kept confidential, that they can withdraw from the study at any stage without giving a reason, and that the data obtained will only be used for scientific purposes. A written Informed Consent Form will be obtained from participants. The principles of the Helsinki Declaration and research and publication ethics will be fully adhered to throughout all stages of the research.

DISCUSSION

Although studies examining the effects of complementary and alternative approaches in the management of premenstrual syndrome (PMS) exist in the national and international literature, studies evaluating the effect of laughter yoga on PMS symptoms are quite limited. Although the literature includes a quasi-experimental study examining the effect of laughter yoga practice on PMS symptoms (18), no study has been found that addresses PMS symptoms and quality of life together and evaluates laughter yoga within a randomised controlled design. Furthermore, existing studies do not evaluate the self-applicability of laughter yoga by individuals and its consideration as a sustainable care model. In this regard, the doctoral thesis aims to contribute to the literature by addressing the sustainability dimension of laughter yoga

in PMS management for the first time.

Laughter yoga offers a multi-component and holistic approach that combines yoga-based movements, rhythmic breathing exercises, and touching specific acupuncture points. Being a low-cost, easy-to-learn practice with no risk of side effects makes laughter yoga a highly applicable method for PMS management. Thanks to this multi-component structure, it allows for the simultaneous treatment of the physical, emotional, and cognitive symptoms of PMS. It is expected to increase young women's body-mind awareness, strengthen their ability to cope with symptoms, and improve their quality of life. This study aims to evaluate the sustainability of the method at an individual level by monitoring the participants' ability to integrate laughter yoga practices into their daily lives after the training and application process. Thus, the goal is to position laughter yoga not only as a short-term intervention but also as a self-care behaviour that can be sustained over the long term.

However, certain methodological considerations should be taken into account when interpreting the findings. Due to the nature of the intervention, blinding of participants and researchers could not be implemented. This lack of blinding may increase the risk of expectancy effects and response bias, particularly in self-reported outcome measures. Therefore, the findings should be interpreted with caution in terms of internal validity.

The findings from this doctoral dissertation are expected to provide information on the potential role of laughter yoga in terms of its effects on premenstrual syndrome symptoms and quality of life in young women. Furthermore, it is considered that laughter yoga, being a low-cost and safe practice, can be evaluated as an alternative approach

in premenstrual syndrome management. The study results are expected to offer a framework for integrating laughter yoga into nursing practice as a sustainable and holistic care approach; and to contribute to clinical practice, health policies, and future intervention studies.

Limitations

As the results of this study are limited to young women enrolled at the Bilecik Health Services Vocational School, it is considered a fundamental limitation that they cannot be directly generalised to the entire population. The extent to which participants will adhere to the 'laughter practices' included in the programme after the 4-week (8-session) laughter yoga programme is a variable beyond the researcher's control. Furthermore, although collecting data using scales carries the risk of recall bias and subjectivity, this will be minimised by standard data collection timings. The possibility of information sharing (contamination risk) among participants sharing the same social environment may complicate the complete isolation of the groups. To manage this risk, the control group will be informed that they are in a waiting period, and participants will be asked to sign a confidentiality agreement during the consent phase. Finally, in accordance with ethical principles, providing the control group with limited information restricted to a single session may limit this group's full access to the long-term gains achieved by the intervention group.

CONCLUSION

This study protocol presents a holistic and innovative randomized controlled trial model addressing the management of premenstrual syndrome from the perspective of laughter yoga. With its multi-component structure, it aims to support the biopsychosocial integrity

of the individual. In this context, the study represents an approach, addressed in a limited number of studies in the literature, that aims to strengthen young women's perception of control over their own health processes. The findings are expected to guide nursing practice and contribute to the development of evidence-based practices as a low-cost, accessible, self-administered, and sustainable holistic care model for alleviating premenstrual syndrome symptoms and improving quality of life.

Future research should focus on conducting studies with larger and more diverse populations to enhance generalisability. Additionally, long-term follow-up studies are recommended to evaluate the persistence of intervention effects. Comparative studies examining laughter yoga alongside other non-pharmacological interventions may also provide valuable insights. Furthermore, incorporating objective physiological indicators (e.g., stress-related biomarkers) and evaluating different durations and frequencies of laughter yoga interventions may help to establish optimal implementation protocols.

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